

Research on the Categories of Fine Art Works and Their Influence on Interior Design Space

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Abstract. *The aim of the article* is to study and define the main categories of fine art works in terms of their use in interior design, and based on the formulated results, provide recommendations for the practical project design activity of artists, designers and decorators. *Results.* During the research, the role of fine art works in interior design was analysed, and it was determined that each of them is characterised by a number of categories: compositional; functional; material; stylistic; thematic. *The scientific novelty* consists in the research, analysis and definition of the main categories of fine art works that influence the design of interior space, as well as in the development of recommendations for their application in artistic and project practice. *Conclusions.* The study showed that the use of certain types of categories of fine art works has a significant impact on the interior design for creating the overall functionality and efficiency of space, certain compositional state, increasing effectiveness and aesthetics, revealing the theme and style, environmental aspects in order to achieve comfort and common harmony of the interior space. According to the results, theoretical and practical recommendations were given for creating a harmonious project solution of the interior space in accordance with the types of categories of fine art works determined in the study. *The perspective* of further research is the interaction analysis of art and interior design objects in the context of full-fledged creation of modern spaces, which will allow a deeper understanding of their mutual influence.

Keywords: categories of fine art works; interior space; interior design

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Introduction

In modern interior design, special attention is paid to the unique atmosphere creation through the use of fine art objects in the interior space, the main characteristic of which is not only intuitive perception by the artist and designer, but also the analysis of their internal relationships in object and spatial relations, which gives the space originality, appropriate emotional impression and artistic vision (Pylypchuk & Polubok, 2023; Pidlisna et al., 2023; Pylypchuk et al., 2024). The integration of art in the interior emphasises cultural, ethnic and aesthetic values, as well as expresses individuality, and is an important element of modern design (Nd, 2021; Shen, 2020; Zhu, 2023). The conceptual basis of integration manifests itself according to fine art with its interrelated categories, and unique rules and peculiarities of interior design. Nowadays, the study of fine art categories is

important for understanding the structure and nature of art works, their impact on viewers, and expanding the understanding of cultural, ethnic and aesthetic aspects of art. From the point of view of practical use, defining, understanding and structuring the main art categories can help designers, artists and other professionals create more effective and harmonious visual interior spaces. Thus, the analysis of fine art categories, and the determination of their influence on the design of interior space have a noticeable theoretical and practical significance, contributing to the development of the cultural and artistic potential of society, which makes it relevant, and requires further study.

Recent research and publication analysis. Modern scientific studies, based on critical system analysis and collection of experimental data, confirm that the integration of art into space is one of the key

factors in interior design, visually stimulating and aesthetically enriching the spatial environment, while simultaneously providing effective functionality. For example, a research on maintaining the balance between art and functionality of a space analyses the way in which an art object, intended for interior design projects, can be transformed into a valuable art work, while maintaining its functional treasure (Calvo-Andrés & Vigo-Pérez, 2024). The studies also show how interior design always draws inspiration from art, and this is what helps designers transform their works into the language of design through the characteristics of simplicity and harmony (Hassanein, 2020). Understanding that modern design takes into account eco-friendliness, ergonomics and cost in order to make the interior space functionally effective, and meet necessities of a definite audience, modern authors explore the interaction between design and art in the context of their functional orientation. It is concluded that design interacts with the art sphere, providing inspiration for art, which, in turn, enriches the language of design with new expressive means. At the same time, art maintains its autonomy, resisting a complete merger with design, and it is a continuous subject of debate (Aguilar Tobin & Elizalde García, 2018). In the context of combining creative and technical thinking in design, the influence of fine art on various components of design is analysed, which include "usability", "technology", "reliability", "sustainability" and "aesthetics". An approach with an emphasis on the interdisciplinary impact of fine art as a synergy of creativity due to interdisciplinary addition is offered (Spuzic et al., 2016).

The mutual influence of fine art and interior space is actualised in relation to the problem of the person's emotional state when perceiving the interior environment. Not only the positive, but also the negative impact of fine art on a person and the corresponding possible consequences of perception are analysed (Aumann, 2022). Research is being conducted on the therapeutic effect of fine art, for example, in medical institutions, including hospitals for children. Such a study is aimed at finding appropriate artistic forms in order to create a comfortable atmosphere (Abulawi, 2023). In total, modern research shows that the use of art works in interior design reduces stress, creates harmony, improves mood and general condition, as well as increases the level of life satisfaction in various types of spaces (Mastandrea et al., 2019; Yun, 2020; Kim & Heo, 2021).

In the field of culture and art, new methods and practices emerge within the framework of sustainable development, such as hybrid approaches that combine art, design and sustainable development to explore

unique methods of sustainability improvement. In this field, interaction between scientists and artists has still an early stage. Studies identify based on art practices methods, that can significantly impact the pursuit of a sustainable development agenda by unlocking cognitive knowledge aspects, improving communication, changing attitudes toward nature, and fostering visions of the future (Heras et al., 2021). Accordingly, at the moment, the relationship between fine art and interior space is a topical and intensively researched topic. However, there is a corresponding gap in research regarding the definition of definite categories of fine art, and their influence on the design of the corresponding interior.

It should be noted that the author's previous studies were devoted to art objects in interior design, and their influence on functional and aesthetic characteristics, as well as to the definition of innovative methods of integrating and forming unique colour characteristics, aimed at harmonising modern interior space (Pylypchuk et al., 2023, 2024; Pylypchuk & Polubok, 2023; Pylypchuk & Polubok, 2022). To define the topic of this research, and visually confirm the formulated results, own realised works of artistic and project activities are used (*Gallery*, n.d.).

The aim of the article is to investigate the influence of categories of fine art works on the design of interior space, and, based on the determined results, to provide theoretical and practical recommendations, that can be useful in the process of designing interiors of various purposes.

Results

Modern design is not only a creative work that includes different design methods with the aim of projecting aesthetic and functional qualities of the subject environment, but, first of all, it is also a definition of the design concept of the interior space. Modern design is closely related to art as well, as it includes elements of creative expression and aesthetic perception. Art and design interact in order to create unique and functional art objects, that can be visually appealing, and meet the users' needs at the same time (Calvo-Andrés & Vigo-Pérez, 2024). In the context of design, the term "categories" also means a set of characteristic elements and conditions connected with the use of some artistic object within certain categories. It also includes the interrelationship and interpenetration of its different components that affect its characteristics. Thus, in the context of design, the term "categories" retains specific meanings, which are unique to the fine art. Since design and fine art are related to the general conditioning of spatial art, the use of different categories of fine art is a process of its implementation in the design of certain

characteristic features of interior space. Therefore, fine art works are a key element for formation and creation of a harmonious surrounding space of any type.

Studying the categories of fine art and their subspecies is impossible without presenting them in certain aspects, summarising and further analysing their components. Defining these categories often depends on the specific aim of the interior space and the overall design idea.

As a result of analyzing the relationships between objects of fine art and interior space, the main categories are formulated:

Compositional — the category of compositionality in the interior organisation includes such features as integrity, systematicity, structurality, which involve the individualisation and unique space design with the help of art works, and general structural orderliness of space forms. This category is characterised by the following types and means that create a sense of unity and order: proportionality, principle of placement, large-scale relationship of space and art work, statics and dynamics, symmetry and asymmetry, balance, metric order and rhythmic repetitions, adjusting the size of space with the help of art works, golden ratio, contrast and nuance, principle of dominance, subordination, range of all used shades of colour, etc. (Frieling & Auer, 1954; Marder, 1995; Dodsworth, 2009).

The example (Fig. 1) demonstrates the use of the compositional category in the space decision with the help of a fine art object. Due to the peculiarities of placement and scale ratio, the relief artistic and decorative panel emphasises and attracts the viewer's attention, which creates a single visual combination of two interior areas — the living room and the kitchen. Perception clarity and artistic appropriateness create visual comfort, and contribute to individual designing the space.

Fig. 1. The living room studio interior of the residential apartment, Kyiv, Ukraine. Relief panel "Ethnic motif". Designer: O. Zakutskya. Artists: A. Polubok, O. Pylypchuk. The author's photo (*Decorative wall panel*, 2003).

Functional. This category of art works consists of two main types, utilitarian and aesthetic ones. It includes the necessity to combine the functional interior features with the artistic form in utilitarian and aesthetic senses. The aim of using this category of art works is a logical approach to the functional usage of different types of fine art aids in the interior, taking into account their interaction, as well as ensuring the ability of a certain object to perform its utilitarian and/or aesthetic function in order to achieve specific goals in space. Functionality is the ability of a product, a set of products and an environment to perform certain tasks, or to create conditions for its performance, and the product's compliance with its aim (Marder et al., 1995). In modern world, fine art works are intended for aesthetic, symbolic, functional and meaningful filling of space. They can have a functional meaning, including various forms of modern art (Calvo-Andrés & Vigo-Pérez, 2024; Pylypchuk et al., 2023). The application of the functional category of art works contributes to the creation of practical and effective interior spaces, that contribute to the improvement of the quality of human life.

Fig. 2 shows an example in which art objects (stained glass) are used with a functional (utilitarian/aesthetic) aim, as artistic elements of lighting devices in the pharmacy decoration. Inspired by the work of V. Kandinsky "Blue Sky", abstract forms create associative images and allow the pharmaceutical establishment to attract attention and provide more visitors. Made in the style of fusing, stained-glass inserts perform the utilitarian function of colored lighting in addition to the aesthetic one.

Fig. 2. Stained glass in a pharmacy of Kyiv, Ukraine. Designer: O. Zakutskya (The author's photo (*Gallery*, n.d.)).

Material. Traditional or modern materials and technologies, types of material, specifics, technical possibilities of processing, structure, texture of art works create a corresponding effect on the space

perception depending on the use of a certain material. Aesthetic possibilities of the selected material are directly related to its look, technical characteristics, chemical composition of paints, surface texture and the nature of the coating. They depend on unique properties of the material from which art objects are created (Pylypchuk & Polubok, 2022). Technological properties of materials include operational possibilities (stability, strength, usefulness, reliability), and ergonomic characteristics (comfort, convenience, safety, including compliance with operating conditions and ecological safety in the impact of the general interior space on human health) (Carbon, 2020; Zhou, 2022).

Fig. 3 demonstrates the use of non-standard material in a pharmacy where strict hygienic conditions are required. The artistic and decorative design is made using the "decoupage" technique and ecofriendly materials (paper, acrylic paints and fixing coating), which are resistant to operation, and meet hygienic standards. The unusualness of the used materials used in the functional equipment of the pharmacy makes it effective and comfortable for users.

Fig. 3. Interior of a pharmacy in Kyiv, Ukraine.
Designer: O. Zakutskya. Artist: O. Pylypchuk.
(The author's photo (*Gallery*, n.d.)).

Stylistic. In various stylistic systems, directions, trends, which are inextricably linked with the

corresponding methods and ways of shaping art objects, the category of art works reveals and emphasises a certain style of interiors, their artistic and stylistic direction, depending on the style of the art work, and forms appropriate stylistic features of the interior space. Stylistics of fine art works, reflecting a certain cultural epoch time or style, can help to strengthen the general image of the interior, its artistic expression, and the commonality of external signs of the artistic form in various types of fine art (Bertolino, 2015).

The example (Fig. 4) demonstrates the use of the "Art Nouveau" style in the artistic performance of the restaurant interior design, where the main task of the artistic design is to provide the characteristic stylistic features of this interior, which, in turn, helps to strengthen the general style of the place. Thus, one of the main goals is to create a stylistically expressive and visually attractive interior space in accordance with a chosen style.

Fig. 4. Banquet hall of the "Staryi Mlyn" restaurant,
p. Rakytno, Kyiv region, Ukraine.
Designer: M. Butakova. Artist: O. Pylypchuk
(the author's photo (*The mural*, 2015)).

Thematic. In the thematic category of art works, it is important to reveal and emphasise a certain interior theme depending on the topic and artistic genre of the art object, and the formation of the corresponding thematic and genre features of the interior space. In order to achieve this, it is necessary to take into account the combination of all the constituent elements of the interior, as well as their integral thematic and genre organisation. In this case, the main criterion is the correspondence of the theme of artistic works to the content, and the general topic in the image of the interior space, where the artistic image and idea interact (McCorquodale, 1983).

The example (Fig. 5) demonstrates the use of the "Rally" theme for the children's room. The theme

and genre of the painting (art work) corresponds to the theme of the interior, emphasising characteristic features of the space, and creating a complete and exciting image for children.

Fig. 5. Interior of a living room in Kyiv, Ukraine.
Designer: O. Zakutskya. Artist: O. Pylypchuk.
(The author's photo (*Gallery*, n.d.)).

A comprehensive analysis of the impact of the art object on the interior space shows that all similar works of art can be differentiated into different categories, reflecting unique features and artistic characteristics of the space (Fig. 6).

Thus, using fine art works according to certain categories, it is possible to significantly improve and make the interior space expressive, as well as increase its functional efficiency and quality for pleasant life, creating a favorable aesthetic and comfortable space, psychophysiological comfort, which are the main purpose of interior design for various needs.

Conclusions

The following conclusions can be made: categories in fine art are interconnected features of certain art works that share common characteristics within certain types of categories. They are

Fig. 6. Structural scheme of the influence of different types of categories of fine art works on the interior space (elaborated by the author)

characterised and distinguished by definite types in accordance with needs and tasks in interior design different purposes and functions. A set of interconnected types of categories of fine art objects includes the following: the nature of the composition structure; utilitarianism or aesthetics; performance material and technologies of its usage; general stylistic direction; thematic and genre disclosure of the general concept. Using such a complex of characteristic features of these categories, fine art objects are created and used, influencing the interior design, which is characterised by harmony, functionality, safety and usage ease, and takes into account environmental aspects as well.

Scientific novelty. Studying the categories of fine art provides an understanding of the functional capabilities of art works, and their impact on interior space. Research results can be useful in interior design, architecture, media and visual communication. They contribute to the development of scientific theories, as well as can be applied in the process of designing interiors of various purposes.

The perspective of further research can be analysing the interaction of art objects and interior design in the aspect of the full modern spaces creation. This will allow a deeper understanding of their mutual influence and interaction, which in turn will lead to the development of more effective methods and techniques in the sphere of artistic interior design.

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Дослідження категорій творів образотворчого мистецтва та їхнього впливу на дизайн інтер'єрного простору

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Анотація. *Мета статті* — дослідити та визначити основні категорії творів образотворчого мистецтва в аспекті їхнього використання в дизайні інтер'єру; на основі сформульованих результатів надати рекомендації для практичної проєктної діяльності художників, дизайнерів, декораторів. *Результати дослідження.* Проаналізовано роль творів образотворчого мистецтва в дизайні інтер'єру та визначено, що кожен з них характеризується низкою категорій: композиційна, функціональна, матеріальна, стилістична, тематична. *Наукова новизна* полягає у дослідженні, аналізі та визначенні основних категорій творів образотворчого мистецтва, які впливають на дизайн інтер'єрного простору, зокрема в розробці рекомендацій щодо їхнього застосування в художній і проєктній практиці. *Висновки.* Використання визначених видів категорій творів образотворчого мистецтва значно впливає на дизайн інтер'єру для створення загальної функціональності та ефективності простору, певного композиційного стану, підвищення ефектності й естетичності, розкриття тематики та стилю, екологічних аспектів з метою досягнення комфортності та загальної гармонійності інтер'єрного простору. За результатами дослідження було надано теоретично-практичні рекомендації для

створення гармонійного проектного рішення інтер'єрного простору відповідно до визначених видів категорій творів образотворчого мистецтва. *Перспективи* подальших досліджень передбачають аналіз взаємодії об'єктів мистецтва та дизайну інтер'єрів у контексті повноцінного створення сучасних просторів, що дасть змогу глибше зрозуміти їхній взаємний вплив.

Ключові слова: категорії творів образотворчого мистецтва; інтер'єрний простір; дизайн інтер'єру

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